

Proposed Stress Management Strategies to Accelerate Organizational Change at Greeneration Foundation: A Change Management Approach

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ABSTRACT: Nowadays, climate change and other forms of environmental degradation area among defining challenges at present. Moreover, these several things are not only experienced in Indonesia, as well as other countries experiencing the same problem. To overcome the existing problems, of course, there needs to be joint synergies from all elements of society and the government to answer them. Greeneration Foundation (GF) as a member of Indonesian Philanthropy aims to advance philanthropy and contribute to the goals of social justice and sustainable development in Indonesia. In 2022, the Greeneration Foundation is rearranging and consolidating its business foundations, product research and development, and business ideas based on funding sources coming from the individuals themselves. Furthermore, this changing of organization foundations doesn't mean it doesn't cause problems for the employee at Greeneration Foundation. Meanwhile, in undergoing these changes not all individual organizations are able to adapt or cope with the changes made, so of course there are impacts felt by individuals such as tension or stress. Therefore, the authors conducted research related to the correlation of work stress and organizational changes carried out by the Greeneration Foundation to serve as evaluation material for the Greeneration Foundation. This research was conducted on Greeneration Foundation employees with the aim of knowing the correlation between work stress and organizational changes faced by employees at Greeneration Foundation. In this study the authors collected data using a questionnaire with a total sample of 30 respondents and used a type of sample that is saturated sample. The data analysis technique used is quantitative analysis with the linear regression method using the help of the IBM SPSS Statistics program. Based on the results of the research conducted, it shows a level of work stress of 59.0% and organizational change of 68.0% which is in a fairly high category. Based on the following results, work stress and organizational change have a positive and significant correlation with a correlation value of 63.9%. Based on this research, the high level of work stress certainly has the potential to become even higher if proper management is not carried out, especially in the individual and organizational aspects. So that the Greeneration Foundation needs to manage the stress level of employees in order to accelerate organizational changes.

KEYWORDS: Change Management, Organizational Change, Workstress, Workstress Management.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, climate change and other forms of environmental degradation area among defining challenges at present. Environmental damage and natural disaster is a feature of our present. It's likely continuation will define. Our future and, in particular, the future of our life, our economic. Nowadays, The rapid increase in human population and the development of information and communication technology is not balanced with human behavior in socializing with other humans and their environment. This changing are suspected because the human behaviour itself which increasingly ignores its social life which tend to be individualistic. Moreover, these several things are not only experienced in Indonesia, as well as other countries experiencing the same problem. To overcome the existing problems, of course, there needs to be joint synergies from all elements of society and the government to answer them.

The role of the society or community is important as it is an element of the pentahelix theory which includes government, community, academics, businessmen, and the media. (Amrial et al, 2017).The role of social communities and non-profit organizations is considered vital to overcome existing problems. Social entrepreneurship that has responsibility and benefits the environment and society (Roper and Cheney in Saefulloh and Gandara, 2021). Greeneration Foundation (GF) as a member of Indonesian Philanthropy aims to advance philanthropy and contribute to the goals of social justice and sustainable development in Indonesia. In 2022, the Greeneration Foundation is rearranging and consolidating its business foundations, product research and

development, and business ideas based on funding sources coming from the individuals themselves. Furthermore, this changing of organization foundations doesn't mean it doesn't cause problems for the employee at Greeneration Foundation. Meanwhile, in undergoing these changes not all individual organizations are able to adapt or cope with the changes made, so of course there are impacts felt by individuals such as tension or stress. These conditions of stress cannot be avoided because the causes of stress appear in every area of life, one of which is workstress. Davis and Newstrom in Anugrahi (2017) said that workstress influences a person's emotions, thought processes, and physical health. If it becomes too high, it may affect that person's capacity to adapt to the new environment. Besides that, according to Suprihanto and Hadi in Angraini and Wahjono (2022) said that stress is a consequence of every action and environmental situation that creates excessive psychological and physical demands on a person. Mangkunegara (2017:157) also said that workstress is a feeling experienced by an employee who feels pressured by his work. Furthermore, workstress should not be ignored. The company needs to be prepared to be open with the employee about their stress, otherwise, fear and uncertainty will continue to be a factor that can lower morale and inhibit the successful implementation of desired changes at all organizational levels. Therefore, companies must also pay attention to how later employees can work well and also be comfortable in order to achieve success in organizational change. In Greeneration Foundation itself, they don't have tools to analyze the employee condition in the company and also to know the reasons of workstress condition. Through this research, the authors try to propose the best strategy regarding to manage workstress of the employee of Greeneration Foundation in order to implement, develop, and accelerate organizational change within the company.

LITERATURE REVIEW

An organization has a collection of individuals with common aims and objectives within the company. To achieve the goals, the organization requires the existence of behaviour between individuals that affect the organization. Therefore, it is necessary to have skills in understanding organizational behavior. According to Robbins and Judge (2018:33) explain that organizational behaviour is a field of science that studies employee that influence of organizational performance. An organizational behavior focuses on situation that are related to employee. Organizational behavior is a systematic study to study how humans behave individually, as a group and how this behavior can affect individual and group performance and ultimately affect organizational performance (Bangun, 2021). From this explanation it can be concluded that employees who experience stress will affect the performance of the organization itself, including the changes of organization.

Furthermore, workstress is a state of employees who are under pressure at work and can have an impact on many things, workstress itself is influenced by many things. According to Robbins and Judge (2018:327) state that stress is a condition that changes as a person meets with opportunities, requests, and resources in other people, and that the demands of the job take priority above personal outcomes. There are many impacts of workstress. According to Robbins and Judge (2018:331) the impact of workstress is divided into three, namely physiological symptoms, psychological symptoms and behavioral symptoms. Physiological symptoms are symptoms of stress that affect health such as changes in metabolism, increased heart rate, blood pressure, headaches and heart attacks. Psychological symptoms are symptoms of stress that affect the mentality of employees in the form of tension, anxiety, irritability, boredom and procrastination profession. While behavioral symptoms are symptoms of changes in behavior in the workplace such as reduced productivity, increased absenteeism, increased turnover rates and changes in eating habits. Another opinion explained by Kinicki and Fugate (2018:660) stated that workstress has an organizational and individual impact.

Therefore, Organizational change is a process of changing an organization from its current state to the expected future condition. According to Winar in Anugrahi (2017) stated that organizational change is the act of shifting an organization from the current situation to future conditions according to what is desired in order to increase its effectiveness. Another opinion explained by Triana, *et al.* in Laihad *et al.* (2019), Organizational change is a process in which the organization moves from its current state to the desired future to increase the effectiveness of its organization. Furthermore, Robbins in Rahadian (2013) stated that basically all the changes made lead to an increase in organizational effectiveness with the aim of improving the ability of the organization to adapt to environmental changes and changes in the behavior of members of the organization. Organizational change is a systematic process, namely a change from a topic that is only of interest to academics and practitioners to something of interest to corporate executives for organizational survival (Lewin in Rahadian, 2013). From the explanation of the experts above, it can be concluded that organizational change is a process of improved ways of using resources and capabilities with the aim of enhancing the organization's ability to create value and enhance the desired outcomes for stakeholders.

Furthermore, In order to propose the stress management strategy to accelerate organizational change in Greeneration Foundation, author uses 8 steps to accelerate change by Kotter, 2014. These tools are useful for providing strategic steps from upstream to downstream that must be implemented by Greeneration Foundation to be able to implement change effectively and efficiently. These 8 steps could help Greeneration Foundation to accelerate the change so that the process leading to these changes can be completed quickly and correctly so that the company does not fall behind other businesses. This becomes very relevant to the topic of this research, where an acceleration is needed to improve organizational goals through the implementation of change in the organization. 8 (eight) steps to accelerate change in organization by Kotter (2014), namely, Create a sense of urgency, Build a guiding coalition, Form a strategic vision and initiatives, Enlist a volunteer army, Enable action by removing barriers, Generate short-term wins, Sustain acceleration, and Institute change. From the explanation of the experts above, the author will be used a change management theory by Kotter as a guidance theory to implement Stress Management Strategy on Implementing Change at Greeneration Foundation.

Furthermore, In this study, the authors used the theory of workstress by Kreitner and Kinicki (2014: 290) with the dimensions of individual stressors, group stressors, organizational stressors and extra-organizational stressors and the theory of organizational change by Daft in Anugrahi (2017) with dimensions of preparation, acceptance, and institutionalization. The following is the framework of this research is shown below.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

RESEARCH METHOD

In this research, the author uses a quantitative research, wheres the quantitative research is a type of research that produces discoveries that can be achieved using statistical procedures or other methods of quantification (measurement) (Sujarweni, 2020). Sugiyono (2019:16) explains that quantitative research is a research method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to examine certain populations and samples, collecting data using research instruments, data analysis is quantitative or statistical, with the aim of testing established hypotheses. Furthermore, the authors also conducted in-depth interviews to deepen the findings from the quantitative results obtained. In this research, the authors used a data collection technique using a questionnaire (questionnaire) by making several questions or written statements and then distributing them to respondents to be able to answer them online. According to Sugiyono (2019:199) questionnaires are an efficient data collection technique if researchers know with certainty the variables to be measured and know what can be expected from respondents. Quantitative research method could help the author to describe the phenomena and explore business issues that occur at the Greeneration Foundation, so the author can formulate the stress management strategy for the Greeneration Foundation in implementing change.

Furthermore, in this research the author will use a saturated sample. A saturated sampling itself is a sampling technique when all members of the population are used as a sample. This is often done when the population is relatively small, less than or equal to 30 people, or research that wants to make generalizations with very small errors (Sujarweni, 2020). Another term for a saturated sample

is a census where all members of the population are sampled. From the explanation of the expert above, in this research the author can use a total of population at Greeneration Foundation, which is 30 numbers of employee.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Respondents Profile

The general description of the characteristics of the respondents of Greeneration Foundation employees based on gender can be explained in the pie chart as follows:

Figure 2. Characteristic of Respondents Based on Gender

The description above shows the characteristics of Greeneration Foundation employee respondents from 30 employees based on gender. There are 11 male employees with a percentage of 37% and 19 female employees with a percentage of 63%. From data above it is concluded that the dominant employees of Greeneration Foundation are female employees.

Validity Result

A. Workstress

Based on table result of the validity test with the help of IBM SPSS, it shows that the results of the validity test of all question items on the workstress have a total r count value greater than r table 0.374. Based on this, it can be concluded that the results of the validity test of the workstress in this study are declared valid and can be continued in further research.

B. Organizational Change

Based on table result of the validity test with the help of IBM SPSS, it shows that the results of the validity test of all question items on the organizational change have a total r count value greater than r table 0.374. Based on this, it can be concluded that the results of the validity test of the organizational change in this study are declared valid and can be continued in further research.

Reliability Result

Based on table result of the reliability test with the help of IBM SPSS, it shows that the reliability test results of the workstress have a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.786, and organizational change has a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.864, each of these variables has a higher Cronbach's Alpha value greater than 0.60 so that it can be concluded that the reliability test results from the variables of workstress, and organizational change in this study were declared reliable and could be continued in further research.

Classic Assumption Test

A. Normality Test

According to Sujarweni (2020: 120) the normality test aims to measure whether our data has a normal distribution or not, so that it can be used in parametric statistics, if the data is not normally distributed, non-parametric statistics can be used. In this study the data is said to be normally distributed if the results of the significance value are greater than 0.05.

Table 1. Result of Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		Unstandardized Residual
N		30
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0E-7
	Std. Deviation	3,18580805
	Absolute	,199
Most Extreme Differences	Positive	,156
	Negative	-,199
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1,092
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,184

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

Source: Author, 2023

Based on table 1 above, it shows that the significance value in this study is 0.184, which means > 0.05 so that it can be stated that this study is normally distributed and deserves to be continued for further research.

B. Linearity Test

In this study the authors used the significant value to see the results of the linearity test. The provisions of the linearity test to experience linearity if the sig linearity is < 0.05 and the deviation from linearity is sig > 0.05 . The following are the results of the linearity test analysis in this study:

Table 2. Results of Linearity Test

ANOVA Table

				Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Organizational change * workstress	Between Groups	(Combined)	from	31,213	3	10,404	,581	,633
		Linearity		,082	1	,082	,005	,947
		Deviation from Linearity		31,131	2	15,565	,869	,431
	Within Groups		465,754	26	17,914			
	Total		496,967	29				

Source: Data that has been processed by the author, 2023

Based on table 2 above, it shows that the significance F-linearity value is $0.005 < 0.05$ and the deviation from linearity value is $0.431 > 0.05$ so that this study can be declared variables have a significant linear relationship and is feasible to proceed to further research.

C. Heteroscedasticity Test

According to Sujarweni (2020: 159) the heteroscedasticity test has a purpose to test the difference in residual variance from one observation period to another. In this study the authors conducted a heteroscedasticity test using the Scatterplot test. The Scatterplot test itself can be declared free from heteroscedasticity if the Scatterplot data points spread above and below or around the number

0, the data points do not cluster together only above or below only, spread data points cannot form a pattern line widens then narrows and widens again, the distribution of data points is not patterned. Following are the results of the heteroscedasticity test in this study:

Figure 3. Result of Heteroscedasticity Test

Based on table 3 above, it shows that the distribution of data points is not patterned and the data points do not cluster together only above or below only, so that this study can be declared free from heteroscedasticity and is feasible to proceed to further research.

ANALYSIS

To deepen the results of research analysis, the author has obtained through the in-depth interview process and selected it based on its relevance to the research by comparing data from questionnaires with the key informants. The author intends to compare the data from questionnaires with relevant cases, interviews, sources linked to research problems. So that the facts and information produced can be trusted and their validity is considered using this technique. The data is based on the results of interviews with 5 informants and using the guidance theory "8 steps to accelerate change" as follows:

No.	Key Point	Informants				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Organizational change is an urgent matter in the Company so that the company can sustain in the long run.	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
2	Taskforce or special team required for organizational change acceleration.	YES, I realizes that special team is needed to accelerate change, but so far there is no change team has been formed and is still working partially on change action.	Yes, Greeneration Foundation should have organizational change team to accelerate the implementation of change and to be more focused. Because it is part of Greeneration Foundation priorities.	Yes, but even though Greeneration Foundation does not yet have a change team, I believes that with the presence of an change team, the acceleration of change implementation will be run according to a schedule.	YES, I realizes that a special team is needed to accelerate change for the temporarily.	YES, currently in practice, this team receives direct direction from the Director to work on changes in parallel by also running programs that already existed at the Greeneration Foundation.
3	It takes strategic initiatives, action plans and roadmaps in the implementation of organizational change.	Yes, Greeneration Foundation believes that strategic initiatives and roadmaps are needed. However, until now Greeneration does not have it yet.	Yes, Greeneration Foundation is aware of this and Greeneration Foundation has strategic initiatives, action plans and roadmaps but not quite clearly.	Yes, Greeneration Foundation believes that strategic initiatives and roadmaps are needed. However, until now Greeneration does not have it yet.	Yes, Greeneration Foundation is aware of this and Greeneration Foundation has strategic initiatives, action plans and roadmaps but not quite clearly.	Yes, Greeneration Foundation is aware of this and Greeneration Foundation has strategic initiatives, action plans and roadmaps but not quite clearly.
4	Collaboration between employees is needed for Organizational change acceleration in terms of create strategic initiatives, action plans, and roadmaps.	YES, it needs collaboration.	YES, it needs collaboration.	YES, it needs collaboration.	YES, it needs collaboration.	YES, it needs collaboration.
5	The biggest obstacle or challenge in implementing change	Understanding the urgency of change, conflict of interest.	Clear guidance and task.	Understanding the urgency of change.	Clear guidance and task.	Clear guidance and task.
6	Short term goals to be achieved	Understanding the urgency of change, create roadmaps, rewards and punishment.	In the near future, the Company needs to focus and be consistent on changing transition with create a special team.	This organizational change must be understood as a common goal, because basically Greeneration Foundation wants business processes to uphold business sustainability.	Organizational change is a common goal, it cannot be run by the several employees. Therefore, collaboration is needed.	Immediately apply KPI standards well and have a good KPI score and contribute to the achievement of change.
7	What do you think needs to be improved in Greeneration Foundation?	It is important to create rewards and punishments related to the implementation of change.	There must be a clear roadmap, along with key activities, so that change goals can be gradually achieved.	In order to implementing change, clear communication & coordination is needed both internally and externally.	Have good leadership, credible committee, good mechanism of change implementation and evaluation.	Have good leadership, credible committee, good mechanism of work implementation and evaluation.

Figure 4. In-Depth Interview Result

Based on the in-depth interview and the research analysis that authors mentioned before, the authors try to summarized the analysis into three points, as follow:

A. Workstress

The results of the descriptive analysis of the workstress variable were carried out through distributing questionnaires (questions) to 30 respondents at the Greeneration Foundation obtained an average percentage score of 59,0%, based on the distribution of questionnaires (questionnaires) to 30 respondents which were described into seventeen questions it can be concluded that Greeneration employees Foundation has a fairly high level of workstress. As for the respondents' responses regarding the workstress variable, each obtained an average score that was quite varied. Based on statement item (5) in individual stressors obtains the highest average score of 68.97%, meaning that the respondent has a lack of understanding of roles and responsibilities related to their work

position, while statement item (2) obtains an average the lowest average score of 52.0% means that the jobs obtained by the respondents are quite a lot and quite varied.

Furthermore, on the group stressor dimension, item statement (8) has the highest average percentage score of 53.3%, meaning that respondents complain that they do not have enough support from their superiors, while statement item (9) has the lowest average percentage score of 42.67% means that respondents received bad treatment from employees in low category organizations. Furthermore, organizational stressors have the lowest average score on item statement (12) of 58.0%, meaning that it is sufficient to provide work tool support for employees in the organization, while item statement (11) has the highest average score of 72.0%. meaning that the organization is not sufficient to provide clarity of organizational structure and work responsibilities to employees. Furthermore, the extra-organizational stressor has the lowest average score on item statement (16) of 53.3%, meaning that the time it takes respondents to go to work (office) is quite short, whereas item statement (15) has an average the highest score of 70.0% means that the organization does not provide sufficient clarity on organizational structure and work responsibilities to employees. Furthermore, based on these results the group stressor dimension in this variable has the lowest average score of 48.2%, while the organizational stressor dimension has the highest average score of 65.8%, the individual stressor dimension has an average score of 65, 3% and the extra-organizational stressor dimension of 50.8%. Based on this, it can be concluded that the average score on the workplace variable is 59.0%, meaning that Greeneration Foundation employees have a fairly high level of workstress but have the potential to continue to increase if not paid attention to.

B. Organizational Change

The results of the descriptive analysis of the organizational change variables carried out by distributing questionnaires (questionsnaires) to 30 respondents at the Greeneration Foundation obtained an average percentage score of 68.0%, based on distributing questionnaires (questionnaire) to 30 respondents described into fifteen questions it can be concluded that Greeneration Foundation employees have a fairly high level of organizational change. The respondents' responses regarding the organizational change variable for each obtained an average score that was quite varied. Based on statement items (20) in the preparation dimension obtain the highest average score of 67.33%, meaning that the norms that exist within the organization support respondents to implement changes, while statement items (2) obtain an average the lowest average score of 50.0% means that respondents are less involved in providing input regarding work systems and new work policies. Furthermore, on the acceptance dimension, item statement (26) has the highest average percentage score of 78.0%, meaning that decisions are always made by the head of the department, whereas statement item (24) has the lowest average percentage score of 59, 33% means that the respondent only coordinates work with colleagues from the same department. Furthermore, the institutionalization dimension has the lowest average score in item statement (28) of 68.67%, meaning that the division of work divisions carried out by the organization is quite in accordance with the capabilities of employees, while item statement (29) has the highest average score of 82.0% means that respondents always carry out work according to directions from their superiors.

Furthermore, based on these results the preparation dimension in this variable has the lowest average score of 57.8%, while the institutionalization dimension has the highest average score of 76.0%, and the acceptance dimension has an average score of 70.8%. Based on this, it can be concluded that the average score on the workplace variable is 68.0%, meaning that Greeneration Foundation employees have a fairly high level of organizational change but have the potential to be even better, especially in the preparation aspect.

C. The Correlation Between Workstress and Organizational Change

Based on test (r) correlation coefficient in this study shows a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.639 or 63.9%, so it means that the workstress variable has a close correlation of 63.9% to organizational change variables and vice versa for Greeneration Foundation employees. Furthermore, based on these results, the authors conducted an in-depth interview with 5 Greeneration Foundation employees to find out which dimensions or items of workstress have a correlation with organizational change, and vice versa.

Furthermore, the authors found several correlations between statement items or dimensions of each variable. On item no. 4 on the individual dimension of workstress that there is a correlation relationship on item no. 21 on the dimension of preparation organizational change. This means that there is a lack of employee involvement in providing their input and ideas into the new work system and new work policy causing differences in expectations from employees and the organization, these differences result in workstress at the individual level of employees being high if this is allowed to continue it will it is very possible that employee motivation in implementing changes also decreases. Furthermore, it was proven in item no 4 in the in-depth interviews conducted,

out of a total of 5 employees, they responded that collaboration between parties was needed in order to accelerate change, whether in making strategic initiatives, making roadmaps, or action plans.

Furthermore, still in the preparation dimension there is a positive correlation between item no. 18 and item no. 5 on the individual stressor dimension. It can be seen from the employee respondents at the Greeneration Foundation who are of the opinion that the current guidelines within the organization are considered to be less helpful to employees in carrying out their work, these items result in a high level of employee misunderstanding of their duties and responsibilities in completing work. This, again resulted in the individual dimension of the stressor having a high level of stress.

Furthermore, in the dimension of preparation item no. 19 there is no positive correlation with the group stressor dimension, namely item no. 7. Based on the results of employee respondents, it can be seen that the norms in the company are considered to be less supportive of employees in carrying out their work, but this does not affect respondents in the dimension of group stressor item no 7, namely the level of team cohesiveness at the Greeneration Foundation is considered quite compact so that this keeps employees motivated enough to implement changes, this is evidenced in item no 20 and item no 22 the preparation dimension. Apart from that, it was also proven by in-depth interviews that employees are aware that organizational change is quite urgent so that organizational change is needed.

Furthermore, it is still related to the dimension of preparation in organizational change which is still at a moderate level resulting in the author conducting further discussion regarding the level of preparation carried out by the Greeneration Foundation. Greeneration Foundation employees feel that communication and knowledge regarding current initiative strategies, action plans, and roadmaps are still unclear and poorly understood by employees. In fact, as many as 2 out of 5 interviewed employees said that currently the organization does not yet have a roadmap in order to implement changes, this certainly affects the level of preparation in the organization which is not optimal in implementing changes. On the other hand, employees can actually accept the changes made by the organization, this is evidenced in the acceptance dimension which has a high score, meaning that employees are quite able to accept the changes that occur. Furthermore, in the dimension of institutionalization, it has a high value, which means that employees have no problems with the change initiatives carried out by the organization. However, the preparation stage carried out by the organization which is still not optimal results in stress in several dimensions for employees, namely at the individual level and at the organizational level related to the work directions applied which are still not clear.

CONCLUSION

Workstress and organizational change are two things that go hand in hand, if the organization makes changes it will affect workstress, and vice versa if workstress cannot be managed by the organization then it will hinder organizational change itself. Of course, this is not an easy thing, because like it or not it will be faced by the organization when making changes, therefore the organization must pay attention to the conditions of employee behavior so that organizational changes can run well according to targets and plans. According to this research, the author concludes that:

1. There are several challenges and obstacles faced by Greeneration Foundation related to the implementation change. These challenges and obstacles are regarding conflict of interest, understanding the urgency of change, and lack of clear guidance and task. These things, if not addressed immediately will influence and increase level of workstress in the organization. These things also will seriously hamper the implementation of change.
2. To be able to reduce the level of workstress and accelerate change at Greeneration Foundation. The change management approach with 8 (eight) step of change is needed so the organization can move faster towards the expected change.

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